

Parental Involvement in Distance Learning on Intermediate Pupils at General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School, Valenzuela City

Cherie Pearl D. Florida

Schools Division Office of Valenzuela, Philippines, General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School

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Abstract: The Covid-19 pandemic created major adjustments to different aspects of society. Distance learning was a means to continue education amidst the pandemic. Teachers can remotely deliver lesson content and instruction. Students can learn in the comforts of their homes through online platforms. During the absence of instructors, the parents are the ones who guide them. In relation to this, the researcher aimed on assessing the parental involvement of intermediate pupils at General Tiburcio de Leon Elementary School in Valenzuela City, Philippines. In the study, the researcher employed the descriptive-correlational research design through gathering data with using an adapted survey questionnaire. Hence, it was assessed that there was a significant difference in values and attitudes on education when grouped according to gender and in the academic management and guidance when grouped according to family monthly income. Furthermore, it was also evaluated that there is no significant relationship on the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile particularly between age, and highest educational attainment and number of children, between the number of children and number of children enrolled, between grade level and the number of children enrolled. However, a significant relationship was found between monthly family income and homework management and guidance, and values and attitudes on education. Hence, based on the findings of the study, the researcher used the results to develop an intervention program to strengthen the parental involvement in intermediate level.

Keywords: Distance Learning, Parental Involvement, Management, Attitudes, Teachers.

Introduction

Distance learning is a non-traditional method of teaching in which instruction takes place between a teacher and students who are geographically remote from one another (Dangle and Sumaoang, 2020). The method of teaching is through the utilization of technologies such as the internet and online platforms like Google Classroom, Google Meet, and Zoom Meeting. Through these platforms, virtual classes are possible and classes are more advantageous for the current pandemic circumstance. Parents collaborate with teachers as home facilitators since education is no longer limited to the classroom (FlipScience, 2020).

Although, some students, specifically those in the elementary level, are needing actual

communication as it is critical for their obtaining of information, especially during their young age and that is why they struggle and get easily distracted by other things at home, affecting their academic learning. With this, parents are also affected by the difficulty and try to find ways to lessen the burden that their children are carrying (Magsambol, 2020).

To help the children, they are the ones who go to the schools to fetch the modules prepared by the teachers. During the process of answering the modules assigned to their children, they offer them help and guidance to ease the difficulty that the pupils are facing. After accomplishing all the modules, the parents are likewise the ones to submit them back to the teachers and speak with them if there are specific concerns raised by the student. However, given the fact that most parents want to be more involved, there are several challenges occur such as most parents are working full-time and they were not well-equipped. The Philippines is far too unprepared for the sudden proposal of online learning (Kritz , Manila Times 2020).

This pandemic became a challenge for the educational sector and to teachers nationwide. To strengthen the academic resilience of students, it involves strategic planning and detailed practice involving the whole school community to help these vulnerable young people do better than their circumstances might have predicted. One of the most important elements of success in the distance learning set-up is the active parental involvement in students' academic endeavors. Parents are considered as one of the stakeholders of the school community and play immense roles in the transformation of the child. Therefore, the degree of participation that parents have in their child's education and school, must be realized (Bartolome et al., 2017).

Parental Involvement can be defined as the cooperation that the parents make towards the schooling of his/her children (Martinez, 2017; Goodall 2001). During the absence of the child's instructors, the parents are the ones who guide them and assist them in their education. In the children's learning cycle, parental inclusion is important as children will overall hold on to what can be seen and experienced through their natural environment (Prior and Gerard, 2017), particularly when they are given the opportunity to communicate with their parents (Athey, 2017). Since the family is usually the primary source of a child's learnings, cooperation is an important factor for child's academic readiness (Rieber and Robinson, 2019).

In the United States, the parents are effectively taking an interest in their children's schooling and the purpose for this involvement is that they realize what are the things that can do useful for their kids and what is required for them to continually learn. When a student's performance is observed at home, they behave accordingly at school, listen in class, and therefore do tasks more effectively and efficiently (Federal , 2019) In this case, there is a bond between the parent and the school. Some of the parents offer to volunteer in the school and partake in activities (Stein & Thorkildsen, 2019), and act as paraprofessionals in the classroom organization (Gestwicki, 2017). Schools likewise give educational programs that are centered around the progress of the children as well as their opportunity to learn. They also suggest the parents be engaged with the children's schooling in methods of going to gatherings, events, perusing with the children, and going to family-oriented workshops (Gestwicki, 2017). Moreover, research shows thatparent-teacherconferences,as wellas ratesofhomework assistance and communication with teachers outside of conferences, have been decreasing since 2016 (Benner and Quirck , 2020). This argument suggests that parents are becoming less engaged in their children's education which results to child's low academic achievement.

In the Philippines parents are known to be supportive and compassionate (Jabar , 2020). In Filipino family culture, they value their children's education (Reyes & Resurreccion, 2015). Filipino parents believe that education is the key to get out of poverty (Garcia , 2019). This

assurance in giving their children uphold shows in their interest in schools, for example, participating in school activities and attending to parent-teacher meetings. With the care that Filipino parents give, it is basically comparable to the worldwide setting (Hill and Taylor, 2019). Unfortunately, because of the country's main challenge, which is poverty, parent involvement in the Philippines still needs to improve, especially in terms of motivating parents to participate actively in the child's learning at home and in school. Having strong relationships of schools, teachers and parents will result in higher learning of children (Nierva 2009).

In line with this, the researcher conducted the study as it is timely and relevant with the current situation wherein more than a year has passed since major health protocols were established against the virus which included the utilization of distance learning. The researcher deemed it necessary to check upon the status of how parents are involved in the academics of their children most especially they are the ones that act as a substitute for the teachers which makes them vital to the achievement of learning of their children. The researcher also conduct the study within the selected research locale, particularly in General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School as it is situated in a highly urbanized city which means the population of the school is much larger and can provide diverse data and information that can be useful to the study. Also, given the population of the school having more students makes it harder to monitor their academic achievement, thus the study and its output could act to address one of the challenges that it faces which is upholding quality education. The study provided helpful insight to guide schools like the research locale in developing methods and strategies that incorporate parental engagement to improve the efficacy of distance learning amidst the pandemic.

The study aimed to provide an overview about how the parents manage and guide the pupils in their homework, and to know the value of education for students and their attitude towards it, specifically the intermediate pupils in General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School. This will help teachers, students, and as well as parents to further understand the significance of involvement in education. Thus, the study identified the parental involvement on intermediate pupils in General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary school.

Statement of the Problem

This study was intended to determine the level of parental involvement on intermediate pupils of General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School in Valenzuela City. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3 Highest Educational Attainment; 1.4 Occupation;
 - 1.5 Number of children;
 - 1.6 Number of children enrolled in intermediate level;
 - 1.7 Grade level of children enrolled in intermediate level;
 - 1.8 Number of hours spent for children's modular instruction; 1.9 Monthly family income
2. What is the level of parental involvement in distance learning on the intermediate pupils in terms of;
 - 2.1. Communication with Teachers;
 - 2.2 Academic Management and Guidance;

2.3. Values and Attitudes on Education?

3. Is there a significant difference in the parental involvement in distance learning on the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile?
4. Is there a significant relationship in the parental involvement in distance learning on the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile?
5. What intervention program may be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Methods

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. The researcher chose this kind of research design as it was the most appropriate method to examine and describe the relationship of the variables which are the level of parental involvement and respondents' demographic profile. Through the use of a descriptive-correlational design the researcher was able to get a clear picture when it comes to the current status of parents' involvement on the distance learning of their children. This in turn served as a basis in devising the output of the study which is a proposed intervention program aimed to strengthen the parental involvement on the academic achievement of pupils.

A descriptive correlational approach is typically a research design wherein the researcher intends to describe the association between variables without having to establish a cause-and-effect relationship. In this kind of research design, it utilizes a correlation coefficient to which reveals the extent or degree of relationship among sets of scores or variables. Likewise, this assessment suggested that the researcher does not try manipulating the variables nor the scores gathered. In order to established a relationship among the variables this method would solely rely on the use of correlation statistics (Quaranta, 2017).

Research Respondents

The research respondents of the study were parents of intermediate pupils at General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School in Valenzuela City. They are the chosen respondents as they are the primary people involved and concerned with their children's academic achievement especially under the circumstance of the implementation of distance learning due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

The parents of pupils from General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School were diverse in terms of age, family structure, educational background, occupation, number of children, socio-economic status and level of involvement in their children's distance learning. However, what they do have in common was that they have children enrolled at General Tiburcio Elementary School and were continuing their education through distance learning amidst the pandemic.

Population and Sampling

The objective populace for this examination were parents of intermediate pupils of General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School which is situated in Valenzuela City. The researcher utilized purposive sampling. The reason for this sort of inspecting technique was the respondent's readiness and accessibility. The study employed Slovin's formula for the researcher to have the appropriate number of respondents for the sample size from its population. Based from the table below the sample size for Grades 4, 5, and 6 are 107, 111, and 115 parents of intermediate pupils from General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School respectively which gives a total number of 333 respondents who were engaged in the study.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Sample Size of Research Respondents

Sampling using Slovin's formula			
Grade Level	Entire Population	Percentage	Sample population
Grade 4 - 638	638	32.22%	107
Grade 5 – 661	661	33.38%	111
Grade 6 – 681	681	34.40%	115
Total	1980	100%	333

Research Environment

The study will be conducted in General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School in the 3rd district of Metro Manila, particularly in Valenzuela City.

Valenzuela City is in the northernmost part of Metro Manila and it is considered as a 1st class highly urbanized city located in NCR or National Capital Region of the Philippines. It is part of the 3rd district of Metro Manila along with Caloocan, Malabon, and Navotas. Valenzuela City is comprised of two districts; district 1 has twenty-four (24) barangays and district 2 has nine (9) barangays, with a total of 33 barangays. The city is lined by Quezon City and northern Caloocan City towards the east; Malabon City and southern Caloocan City towards the south; Obando in Bulacan province towards the west; and Meycauayan City, additionally in Bulacan province, towards the north. The land area of Valenzuela City sums up to a total of 44.59 square kilometers (17.22 sq. mi). As declared in the dedicated official website of the city government of Valenzuela, for 2021 it has a projected total population of 675,979 with 164,873 households.

Research Instrumentation

The researcher will use Parent and School Survey (PASS) adopted from Ringenberg, Funk, Mullen, Wilford, and Kramer (2005) as an instrument of information assortment in the study. The PASS questionnaire asks parents to indicate how involved they are in their children's schoolwork, school activities, and collaboration with school personnel. However, the survey questionnaire will be modified to suit the requirements needed in the study. This will be regulated through an online platform for encoding questions. Part I contains the profile of the respondents. The demographic profile variables include their age, gender, the number of children enrolled, and the number of hours involved for children's modular instruction. Part II is a checklist of the respondents' parental involvement on the intermediate pupils in Gen. T. de Leon Elementary School, Valenzuela City in terms of the following variables: their communication with the teacher, homework management and guidance, and discussion of values and attitudes on education. Each of these variables has indicators to be rated by the respondents using the 5-point rating scale, as follows: 5-Strongly Agree (SA); 4-Agree (A); 3-Partially Agree Partially Disagree (U); 2-Disagree (DA); and 1-Strongly Disagree (SD).

Validation of Instrument

Face validation will be made on the research instrument by the research adviser to provide the necessary corrections and revisions to improve its content. After incorporating their suggestions, the revised questionnaire will be submitted for approval. Copies of the approved questionnaire will be tried out in Gen. T. de Leon Elementary School as a part of pilot testing and/or dry-run to test its validity and reliability of the instrument through Cronbach's alpha analysis.

Research Procedure

For the fulfillment of the study, the researcher will choose the reasonable respondents by utilizing convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling method. The researcher will use Parent and School Survey (PASS) adapted survey questionnaire as an information assortment instrument which will help evaluate if there is a critical connection between the demographic profile of the respondents and the parental involvement on the intermediate pupils regarding teaching at a distance. The researcher will encode these in an online stage. a letter of intent will be given to the respondents prior to noting the survey questionnaire along with the data privacy consent.

Data Gathering Technique

In order to commence the data gathering procedure the researcher will first send a letter to conduct the study to Principal of General Tiburcio Elementary School and to the parents who will be the respondents of the study. To facilitate the distribution of the instrument and consider the safety protocols and health threats of the pandemic, the researcher will transfer the instrument into an online platform for making surveys. Once the respondents agree to participate in the study the link for the online survey will be sent to them. The formal transmittal letter will be duly noted and signed by the Dean of the School of Graduate Studies. Data that will be gathered from the online survey will be sorted, tallied, and will be prepared for statistical treatment. The data will be analyzed and will be used in the interpretation and discussion of the results.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher will prepare and send to the principal and respondents the necessary transmittal letter and data privacy consent form to in order to conduct the study. Once the approval of the of the Principal and respondents are obtained the researcher will start the data gathering process. All of the data that will be gathered from the respondents will be treated with utmost privacy and confidentiality, and will be solely for academic purposes only.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Data analysis is considered the most crucial part of the research. In analyzing the obtained data, the researcher will apply percentage as a statistical method for the different variables on the demographic profile of the respondents which encapsulates age, gender, number of children involved, number of hours involved for children's modular instruction and monthly family income. Then, in determining the respondent's parental involvement in the intermediate pupils concerning the communication with the teachers, homework management and guidance, and discussion of values and attitudes on communication. To inspect this, there will be a use of weighted mean analysis utilizing the frequency distribution formula. Furthermore, the F-test ANOVA will also be used to determine whether there is a significant difference between the respondent's level of parental involvement on the intermediate pupils and the respondent's demographic profile. As stated by Frost (2021), ANOVA, the Fisher analysis of variance was developed by Ronald Fisher and it was considered as an extension of the t- and z-tests. It serves as a primary tool to analyze multiple variables at a similar time. It is also used to test the hypothesis that more than two group means are equal. The analyst applies the ANOVA test results in an f-test to produce more information that aligns with the proposed regression models.

Results and Discussion

On the Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 presents the profile of the parents of intermediate pupils of General Tiburcio De Leon Elementary School in Valenzuela City in terms of their age, gender, number of children

enrolled, number of hours spent for children's modular instruction, and monthly family income.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution on the Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Age</i>		
20 – 29 years old	30	9.0
30 – 39 years old	171	51.4
40 – 49 years old	110	33.0
50 years old and above	22	6.6
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	23	6.9
Female	310	93.1
<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>		
No schooling completed	12	3.6
High School Graduate	190	57.1
Bachelor's Graduate	97	29.1
Masteral / Doctoral Graduate	4	1.2
Other Professional Training	30	9.0
<i>Occupation</i>		
Housewife	174	52.3
Teacher	19	5.7
Vendor	9	2.7
Factory Worker	19	5.7
Technician	1	0.3
Business Owner	15	4.5
CSR / Call Center	8	2.4
Government Employee	9	2.7
Office Staff	45	13.5
Driver	2	0.6
OFW	4	1.2
Freelance	6	1.8
Hairdresser / Manicurist	4	1.2
Maid	3	0.9
Therapist	2	0.6
Delivery Services	2	0.6
Nurse	7	2.1
Service Crew	2	0.6
IT Specialist	2	0.6
<i>Number of Children</i>		
1 Child Only	46	13.8
2 – 3 Children	207	62.2
4 – 5 Children	67	20.1
More than 5 Children	13	3.9
<i>Number of Children Enrolled</i>		
1 Child Only	104	31.2
2 – 3 Children	199	59.8
4 – 5 Children	28	8.4
More than 5 Children	2	0.6

<i>Grade Level</i>		
Grade 4	107	32.1
Grade 5	111	33.3
Grade 6	115	34.5
<i>Hours Spent</i>		
0 Hours	3	0.9
1 – 3 Hours	155	46.5
4 – 6 Hours	144	43.2
More than 6 Hours	31	9.3
<i>Monthly Family Income</i>		
Poor	146	43.8
Low Income	128	38.4
Lower Middle	43	12.9
Middle	13	3.9
Upper Middle	3	0.9

Age. As displayed in the table, out of 333 parents of intermediate pupils, 171 (51.4%) were 30 – 39 years old, 110 (33.0%) were 40 – 49 years old, 30 (9%) were 20 – 29 years old, and 22 (6.6%) were 50 years old and above. This implies that most of the respondents are young adults that are aged 30 – 39 years old.

Gender. As shown in the table, out of 333 respondents, 310 (93.1%) were female and 23 (6.9%) were male. This indicates that most of the respondents are women or are possibly mothers of intermediate pupils.

Highest Educational Attainment. As presented in the table, out of 333 parent respondents, 190 (57.1%) were high school graduates, 97 (29.1%) were bachelor's graduates, 30 or (9%) have other professional training, 12 or (3.6%) have no schooling completed, and 4 (1.2%) were masteral / doctoral graduate. This implies that the respondents are knowledgeable enough to respond to the questions provided in the instrument of the study.

Occupation. As shown in the table below, out of 333 respondents, 174 (52.3%) were housewives, 45 (13.5%) were office staffs, 19 (5.7%) were teachers and factory workers, 15 (4.5%) were business owners, 9 (2.7%) were vendors and government employees, 8 (2.4%) were CSR / call centers, 7 (2.1%) were nurses, 6 (1.8%) were freelancers, 4 (1.2%) were OFWs and hairdressers/manicurists, 2 (0.6%) were drivers, therapists, working under delivery services, service crews, and IT specialists, and 1 (0.3) was a technician. This indicates that the respondents are commonly housewives and are related to the majority of the respondents in terms of gender which are females.

Number of children. As presented in the table, out of 333 parents of intermediate pupils, 207 (62.2%) have 2 – 3 children, 67 (20.1%) have 4 – 5 children, 46 (13.8%) has 1 child only, and 13 (3.9%) have more than 5 children. This implies that the most of the parents only have 2 – 3 children.

Number of children enrolled. As displayed in the table, out of 333 respondents, 199 (59.8%) have 2 – 3 children enrolled, 104 (31.2%) have only 1 child enrolled, 28 (8.4%) have 4 -5 children enrolled, and 2 (0.6%) have more than 5 children enrolled. This indicates that the responses of the parents where the majority have 2 – 3 children have enrolled their children in school.

Grade Level. As shown in the table, out of 333 parents of intermediate pupils that are enrolled, 115 (34.5%) are Grade 6 students, 111 (33.3%) are Grade 5 students, and 107 (32.1%) are Grade 4 students. This indicates that the majority of the students are graduating

from the elementary level and are probably in the age range of 11 – 13 years old.

Hours Spent. As presented in the table, out of 333 responses of the hours spent in modular instruction, 155 (46.5%) spend 1 – 6 hours, 144 (43.2%) 4 – 6 hours are spent, 31 (9.3) more than 6 hours are spent, and 3 (0.9%) 0 hours are spent. This implies that the parents of the children enrolled focuses on their child’s learning through modular instruction.

Monthly Family Income. As displayed in the table, out of 333 parents of intermediate pupils, 146 (43.8%) belong to the category poor, 128 (38.4%) belong to the category low income, 43 (12.9%) belong to the category of lower-middle, 13 (3.9%) belong to the category of having a middle income, and 3 (0.9%) belong to the category of upper-middle. This indicates that most of the respondents are probably having a minimum rate in their monthly income possibly, Php 8,000 - Php 10,000 pesos a month.

On the Level of Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Respondents

Table 3 presents the parental involvement in distance learning of the respondents in terms of communication with teachers, academic management and guidance, and values and attitudes on education.

Indicators:	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I listen and respond to the teacher when are is a school related-activity.	4.30	Involved
2. I pay great attention to details on what the teacher is saying.	4.26	Involved
3. I have made suggestions to my child’s teachers about how to help my child learn.	3.78	Involved
4. I suggest methods that the teacher can implement with regards to the learning approach of the pupil/s.	3.67	Involved
5. I always check my child’s strengths and weaknesses in different subject areas.	4.36	Involved
6. I always maintain a good and positive relationship with the teacher.	4.34	Involved
7. I have attended virtual meetings at my child’ school (e.g. Parent Orientation, PTA conferences, Distribution of Module, Issuance of Report Cards, etc.)	4.24	Involved
8. I always utilize the use of the internet and social media platforms to regularly communicate to teachers.	4.18	Involved
9. I constantly update the teacher about the learning status of my child.	3.91	Involved

10. I feel my contribution to my child's education is valuable.	4.33	Involved
General Weighted Mean	4.14	Involved

Table 3. Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils in terms of Communication with Teachers

TABLE 3.1 4.50 – 5.00 Highly Involved 3.50 – 4.4 Involved 2.50 – 3.49 Partially Involved 1.50 – 2.49 Less Involved 1.00 – 1.49 Not Involved

Table 3 shows the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils in terms of communication with teachers that gained an overall weighted mean of 4.14 and a standard deviation of 0.72 which have an interpretation that based on the statement provided above in terms of communication with teachers, the parents are involved. Among the statements presented above, the highest computed mean was 4.36 which came from the statement that the parents always check their child's strengths and weaknesses in different subject areas that also have an interpretation that says that the parents are involved. This implies that the parents are allotting their time in assessing their children to understand them by knowing their strengths and weaknesses in accordance to different subject areas. While the lowest mean computed among the responses of the parents was 3.67 however, this was still able to acquire an interpretation that the parents are involved particularly in suggesting methods that the teacher can implement with regards to the learning approach of the pupil/s.

Indicators:	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I display my child's schoolwork in our home (e.g.hang papers on the refrigerator).	3.68	Involved
2. I would know If my child misbehaved during their online classes.	4.19	Involved
3. I frequently explain difficult ideas to my child when she/he doesn't understand.	4.29	Involved
4. I compliment my child every time he/she does something well during their online classes	4.34	Involved
5. I always know how well my child is doing in school.	4.29	Involved
6. I find ways to make the homework appear easy to understand for my child.	4.26	Involved
7. I find ways to make the homework appear easy to understand for my child.	4.45	Involved
7. I provide proper tools/materials (e.g. pencils, dictionaries, notebooks) for their child/children that they can use in making their school work.	4.09	Involved
8. I make sure that reading books is a regular activity in our home.	4.23	Involved
9. I always ensure that my child would not have delay in homework tasks.	4.22	Involved

10. I give rewards as a motivation for my child to finish his/her homework.	4.20	Involved
General Weighted Mean	4.21	Involved

Table 4. Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils in terms of Academic Management and Guidance

TABLE 3.1 4.50 – 5.00 Highly Involved 3.50 – 4.4 Involved 2.50 – 3.49 Partially Involved 1.50 – 2.49 Less Involved 1.00 – 1.49 Not Involved

Table 4 displays the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils in terms of academic management and guidance that obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.21 and a standard deviation of 0.68 that was interpreted as involved. Among the statement provided above, the statement that says that the parents find ways to make the homework appear easy to understand for their child gained the highest mean of 4.45 and was interpreted that the parents are involved. This indicates that the parents think of ways to easily teach their children how to answer homework from school. Whereas, the lowest mean among the statements is from the statement that says that the parents display their child's schoolwork in their home (e.g. hang papers on the refrigerator). which has a computed mean of 3.68 but was still interpreted as involved.

Table 5. Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils in terms of Values and Attitudes on Education

Indicators:	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I explain to my child the importance of integrity in learning during this pandemic.	4.53	Highly Involved
2 I clarify to my child that he/she must avoid having delay in homework tasks.	4.46	Involved
3. I encourage my child to create learning output with quality.	4.44	Involved
4. I tell my child to record his or her test scores so he or she understands the importance of being honest.	4.44	Involved
5. I explain to my child the value of attending virtual programs (e.g. celebration of United Nations, Fire and Earthquake Drill, etc.) regularly.	4.47	Involved
6. I always clear the sense of honesty and responsibility to my child.	4.58	Highly Involved
7. I bring out the value of having good relationship to teachers and other children.	4.57	Highly Involved
8. I explain to my child that I will only assist him by checking instructions they received from the teachers.	4.47	Involved
9, I give my child the opportunity to express his or her thoughts and feelings after his/her school activities.	4.51	Highly Involved

10. I allow my child to try new activities and praise him for his / her successes	4.51	Highly Involved
General Weighted Mean	4.50	Highly Involved

TABLE 3.1 4.50 – 5.00 Highly Involved 3.50 – 4.4 Involved 2.50 – 3.49 Partially Involved 1.50 – 2.49 Less Involved 1.00 – 1.49 Not Involved

Table 5 presents the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils in terms of values and attitudes in education which gained a general weighted mean of 4.50 and a standard deviation of 0.60 that has an interpretation of highly involved. Among the responses of the parents, the statement that has the highest mean was from the statement that says that the parents always clear the sense of honesty and responsibility to their child wherein it gained a computed mean of 4.58 which has an interpretation of highly involved. This implies that the parents teach more about honesty and responsibility in honing the students' values and attitudes towards education. Whereas among the statements provided the lowest mean computed was 4.44 however, this was still interpreted that the parents are still involved. This was from the statements that say that the parents clarify to their child that he/she must avoid having delays in homework tasks and encourage their child to create learning output with quality.

On Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Respondents when grouped According to their Demographic Profile

Table 6. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Respondents when Grouped According to Age

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Age		Test for Equality of Means		Verbal Interpretation
		F	Sig.	
Communication with Teachers	Between Groups	1.227	.300	Not Significant
Homework Management and Guidance	Between Groups	1.146	.331	Not Significant
Values and Attitudes on Education	Between Groups	1.430	.234	Not Significant

Table 6 displays the significant difference on the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to age. Based on the computed p-value, the following variables which are 0.300 for communication with teachers, 0.331 for homework management and guidance, and 0.234 for value and attitudes on education, it was found out that there was no significant difference in the responses of parent respondents on the variables presented above since their p-value is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is failed to be rejected. This indicates that across all age brackets, the responses of the parent respondents are the same.

Table 7. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Gender

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Gender	Gender	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig. Value	Verbal Interpretation
Communication with Teachers	Male	3.89	0.75	-1.743	.082	Not Significant
	Female	4.16	0.71			
Homework Management and Guidance	Male	3.83	0.80	-2.820	.005	Significant
	Female	4.23	0.66			
Values and Attitudes on Education	Male	4.23	0.77	-1.725	.097	Not Significant
	Female	4.52	0.58			

Table 7 presents the significant difference in the parental involvement in distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to gender. In relation to the results shown above, it was found out that there was no significant difference in the responses of the parent respondents in accordance to gender under the variable communication with teachers and discussion of values on education since their computed p-value are 0.082 and 0.97 respectively, were greater than the p-value of 0.05. However, it was found out that there was a significant difference in the responses of the parents under the variables of academic management and guidance and values and attitudes on education since the computed p-value are 0.005, which are less than the alpha level of 0.05. Thus, for the variable of communication with teachers and discussion of values on education, the null hypothesis is failed to be rejected while for the variable of academic management and guidance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that under homework management and guidance as well as values and attitudes on education the practices of the parents vary according to their gender.

Table 8. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment		Test for Equality of Means		Verbal Interpretation
		F	Sig.	
Communication with Teachers	Between Groups	.614	.652	Not Significant
Homework Management and Guidance	Between Groups	1.259	.286	Not Significant
Values and Attitudes on Education	Between Groups	0.67	.992	Not Significant

Table 8 shows the significant difference on the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to highest educational attainment. In accordance to the computed p-value of the following variables which are as

follows; 0.652 for communication with teachers, 0.286 for homework management and guidance, and 0.992 for values and attitudes on education, it was assessed that there is no significant difference in the responses of the parent respondents when group according to their highest educational attainment since, the computed p-value is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is failed to be rejected. This further implies that despite the differences in educational backgrounds, the responses of the parents do not vary.

Table 9. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Occupation

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Occupation		Test for Equality of Means		Verbal Interpretation
		F	Sig.	
Communication with Teachers	Between Groups	.828	.828	Not Significant
Homework Management and Guidance	Between Groups	.782	.782	Not Significant
Values and Attitudes on Education	Between Groups	.542	.542	Not Significant

Table 9 presents the significant difference in the parental involvement in distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to occupation. Based on the results provided on the table, the computed p-value of the following variables namely, 0.667 for communication with teachers, 0.721 for academic management and guidance, and 0.937 for values and attitudes on education indicates that there is no significant differences in the responses of the parents since the computed p-value were greater than the alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis if failed to be rejected. This indicates that despite the differences in their occupation, the parents are still involved in their child's educational development in terms of communication with teachers, academic management and guidance, and values and attitudes on education wherein, there was little to no difference in their responses.

Table 10. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Respondents when Grouped According to Number of Children

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Number of Children		Test for Equality of Means		Verbal Interpretation
		F	Sig.	
Communication with Teachers	Between Groups	.092	.965	Not Significant
Homework Management and Guidance	Between Groups	.484	.694	Not Significant
Values and Attitudes on Education	Between Groups	.742	.528	Not Significant

Table 10 displays the significant difference on the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to number of children. Based on the results presented on the table, which gives a computed p-value of 0.965 for communication with teachers, 0.694 for academic management and guidance, and 0.528 for

values and attitudes on education, it was found out that there was no significant difference in the responses of the parents because the computed p-value of the following variables is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. Thus, indicating that the null hypothesis is failed to be rejected. This implies that despite the differences in the number of children, the responses of the parents do not vary but they are still involved in their children's academic development.

Table 11. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Number of Children Enrolled

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Number of children Enrolled		Test for Equality of Means		Verbal Interpretation
		F	Sig.	
Communication with Teachers	Between Groups	.475	.700	Not Significant
Homework Management and Guidance	Between Groups	.968	.408	Not Significant
Values and Attitudes on Education	Between Groups	.327	.806	Not Significant

Table 11 shows the significant difference on the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to number of children enrolled. In accordance to the results above, the computed p-value of 0.700 for communication with teachers, 0.408 for academic management and guidance, and 0.806 for values and attitudes on education indicates that there is no significant difference in the responses of the parents because the computed p-value is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is failed to be rejected and implies that the responses of the parents do not vary in accordance to the number of their children enrolled.

Table 12. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Grade Level

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to child's grade Level		Test for Equality of Means		Verbal Interpretation
		F	Sig.	
Communication with Teachers	Between Groups	.269	.764	Not Significant
Homework Management and Guidance	Between Groups	.590	.555	Not Significant
Values and Attitudes on Education	Between Groups	.531	.589	Not Significant

Table 12 shows the significant difference in the parental involvement in distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to grade level. In accordance with the results above, the computed p-value of 0.764 for communication with teachers, 0.555 for academic management and guidance, and 0.589 for values and attitudes on education indicates that there is no significant difference in the responses of the parents because the computed p-value is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is failed to be rejected and implies that the responses of the parents do not vary in accordance to the

grade levels of their children

Table 13. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Hours Spent

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Hours spent in Modular Instruction		Test for Equality of Means		Verbal Interpretation
		F	Sig.	
Communication with Teachers	Between Groups	1.600	.189	Not Significant
Homework Management and Guidance	Between Groups	2.048	.107	Not Significant
Values and Attitudes on Education	Between Groups	1.650	.178	Not Significant

Table 4.8 shows the significant difference in the parental involvement in distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to hours spent. In accordance with the results above, the computed p-value of 0.189 for communication with teachers, 0.107 for academic management and guidance, and 0.178 for values and attitudes on education indicates that there is no significant difference in the responses of the parents because the computed p-value is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is failed to be rejected and implies that the responses of the parents do not vary in accordance to the number of hours spent by the parents on teaching their children.

Table 14. Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Family Monthly Income

Significant Difference on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped According to Family Monthly Income		Test for Equality of Means		Verbal Interpretation
		F	Sig.	
Communication with Teachers	Between Groups	.950	.435	Not Significant
Homework Management and Guidance	Between Groups	2.538	.040	Significant
Values and Attitudes on Education	Between Groups	2.749	.028	Significant

Table 14 shows the significant difference in the parental involvement in distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to family monthly income. In accordance with the results above, the computed p-value of 0.435 for communication with teachers indicates that there is no significant difference in the responses of the parents since the computed p-value is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. However, the computed p-value of 0.040 for academic management and guidance, and 0.028 for values and attitudes on education indicates that there is a significant difference in the responses of the parents because the computed p-value is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected for the variables academic management and guidance and values and attitudes on education and implies that the responses of the parents vary in accordance to their family monthly income.

On Significant Relationship on the Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Demographic Profile

Table 5 shows the relationship on the parental involvement on distance learning of the intermediate pupils when respondents are grouped according to demographic profile.

Table 15. Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Age

	Pearson Correlation	Verbal Interpretation	Sig. Value
Communication with Teacher	-0.072	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.192 ($<0.05 - 0.01$) Not Significant
Academic Management and Guidance	-0.060	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.276 ($<0.05 - 0.01$) Not Significant
Discussion of Values on Education	-0.065	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.235 ($<0.05 - 0.01$) Not Significant

The responses of the participants when correlated with their ages yields the Pearson R. values and Sig. Values that are verbally interpreted as “Not-Significant, Very Weak / Negligible Relationships” for all variables of Parental Involvement. Communication with Teacher, Academic Management and Guidance and Discussion of Values on Education have Pearson R Value of -0.072, -0.060 and -0.065 respectively and its significance level is above 0.05. The results of the study suggest that parental involvement is not highly reliant on the respondent’s age. Regardless of their age, parents participate in their children's education.

Table 16. Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

	Pearson Correlation	Verbal Interpretation	Sig. Value
Communication with Teacher	-0.011	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.845 ($<0.05 - 0.01$) Not Significant
Academic Management and Guidance	-0.098	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.739 ($<0.05 - 0.01$) Not Significant
Discussion of Values on Education	-0.018	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.741 ($<0.05 - 0.01$) Not Significant

The responses of the participants when correlated with highest educational attainment yields the Pearson R. values and Sig. Values that are verbally interpreted as “Non-Significant, Very Weak / Negligible Relationships” for all variables of Parental Involvement. Communication with Teacher, Academic Management and Guidance and Discussion of Values on Education have Pearson R Value of -0.011, -0.098 and -0.018 respectively and its significance level is above 0.05. The result shows that their participation in their children's education is not in the educational attainment of the parents. The majority of the respondents are high school graduates; however, the data shows that their parental involvement in their children's education is comparable to that of other parents.

Table 17. Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Number of Children

	Pearson Correlation	Verbal Interpretation	Sig. Value
Communication with Teacher	-.012	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.829 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Academic Management and Guidance	-.051	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.351 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Discussion of Values on Education	-.041	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.452 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant

The responses of the participants when correlated with number of children yields the Pearson R. values and Sig. Values that are verbally interpreted as “Not-Significant, Very Weak / Negligible Relationships” for all variables of Parental Involvement. Communication with Teacher, Academic Management and Guidance and Discussion of Values on Education have Pearson R Value of -.012, -.051 and -.041 respectively and its significance level is above 0.05. The results reveal that parental participation is unrelated to the number of children they have. Despite having another child, parents are able to devote time to their children's education

Table 18. Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Number of Children enrolled

	Pearson Correlation	Verbal Interpretation	Sig. Value
Communication with Teacher	0.14	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.805 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Academic Management and Guidance	-.003	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.954 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Discussion of Values on Education	-.010	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.852 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant

The responses of the participants when correlated with number of children enrolled yields the Pearson R. values and Sig. Values that are verbally interpreted as “Non-Significant, Very Weak / Negligible Relationships” for all variables of Parental Involvement. Communication with Teacher, Academic Management and Guidance and Discussion of Values on Education have Pearson R Value of 0.14, -.003 and -.010 respectively and its significance level is above 0.05. It shows that the involvement provided by parents does not differ based on the grade level to which their child belongs. It demonstrates that parental involvement is unaffected by the grade level in which their child is enrolled.

Table 19. Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Child's Grade Level

Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Child's grade level	Pearson Correlation	Verbal Interpretation	Sig. Value
Communication with Teacher	-.026	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.640 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Academic Management and Guidance	-.053	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.338 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Discussion of Values on Education	-.056	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.306 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant

The responses of the participants when correlated with child's grade level yields the Pearson R. values and Sig. Values that are verbally interpreted as "Not-Significant, Very Weak / Negligible Relationships" for all variables of Parental Involvement. Communication with Teacher, Academic Management and Guidance and Discussion of Values on Education have Pearson R Value of -.026 , .053 and .056 respectively and its significance level is above 0.05. It shows that the involvement provided by parents does not differ based on the grade level to which their child belongs. It demonstrates that parental involvement is unaffected by the grade level in which their child is enrolled.

Table 20. Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Number of Hours Spent in Modular Instruction

Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Number of Hours Spent in Modular Instruction	Pearson Correlation	Verbal Interpretation	Sig. Value
Communication with Teacher	.027	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.626 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Academic Management and Guidance	.063	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.254 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Discussion of Values on Education	.008	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.878 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant

The responses of the participants when correlated with number of hours spent in Modular instruction yields the Pearson R. values and Sig. Values that are verbally interpreted as "Non-Significant, Very Weak / Negligible Relationships" for all variables of Parental Involvement. Communication with Teacher , Academic Management and Guidance and Discussion of Values on Education have Pearson R Value of .027 , .063 and .008 respectively and its

significance level is above 0.05. This data shows that parental involvement does not depend on the length of time they spend for their children's modular instruction. It's possible that the parents believe that the time they spend is sufficient to meet their involvement in their child's education.

Table 21. Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Monthly Family Income

Significant Relationship on Parental Involvement on Distance Learning of the Intermediate Pupils when Respondents are Grouped according to Monthly Family Income	Pearson Correlation	Verbal Interpretation	Sig. Value
Communication with Teacher	.078	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.158 (<0.05 – 0.01) Not Significant
Academic Management and Guidance	.129	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.018 (<0.05 – 0.01) Significant
Discussion of Values on Education	.127	Very Weak / Negligible Relationship	P= 0.020 (<0.05 – 0.01) Significant

The responses of the participants when correlated with their monthly family income yields the Pearson R. values and Sig. Values that are verbally interpreted as “Not-Significant, Very Weak / Negligible Relationships” in Communication with Teachers. While in these two variables, Academic Management and Guidance and Discussion of Values on Education, the Pearson R Value of are .129 and .127 respectively that are verbally interpreted as “Very Weak / Negligible Relationship and its significance value falls below 0.05 for significance. This means that this Very Weak / Negligible Relationship is significant. It shows that families with larger incomes are more involved in their child's education.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of the study:

1. The respondents are predominantly housewives, ages 30-39 that has a child belongs to intermediate level in General Tiburcio de Leon Elementary School. Most likely, they have 2-3 children with low family income and considered as poor.
2. Based on the findings of the study, respondents showed that they were “Involved” in terms of Communication with teacher and Academic Management and Guidance and “Highly Involved” in Discussion of Values in Education. It can be concluded that the respondents place a high priority on teaching their children values and attitudes towards their education.
3. Tests of differences showed no significant differences in the parental involvement of intermediate pupils at Gen. T. de Leon Elementary School when grouped according to their age, highest educational attainment, occupation number of children and number of children enrolled. This suggests that demographic factors do not lead to differences in the way the respondents get involved in their child's education. However, there is a significant difference showed in terms of gender and monthly family income. This means that respondents vary with regards to their involvement in terms of academic management and guidance. Furthermore, family monthly income is also a significant factor in the differences in the responses of the parents with regards to academic management and

guidance and values and attitudes on education. This indicates that how the parents handle how they teach the children their academic needs and their perspectives on education align with their current income. Here, we can say that the point of view of the parents might be aligned on the thinking that they give pieces of advice on their children to continue striving hard to achieve their goals.

4. Upon assessing the relationship of the following variables, the study found out that there is a significant relationship among the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of monthly income of the respondents, academic management and guidance and values and attitudes on education.

Recommendations

In accordance with the findings of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

1. School leaders may perform a communications assessment to get some knowledge on how teachers are communicating with parents. It is essential for teachers and parents to preserve open lines of communication, especially now that distance learning is the preferred method of instruction.
2. Teachers should encourage parents to share information about their child's strengths and difficulties, such as their child's interests, hobbies and dislikes that may have an impact on his or her learning. This will greatly help teachers to find a way to meet students' needs.
3. It is important to ensure that parents have a positive attitude about education. Parents are the role models of their children. Parents who maintain a good mindset will notice positive results in their child's education.
4. Seek parental help or guidance if needed. It is important that students have open communication with their parents about their education. Through this the parent can understand the needs and difficulties of their child. Thus, making them more involved in their child's education.